

THE INTERACTION OF IODINE AND STARCH. PART I

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Titration of solutions of amylose, potato starch and shoti starch with iodine have been carried out using a potentiometer and a photo-electric colorimeter respectively, for measuring the iodine activities and the intensities of colour, at different concentrations of starch and iodine and in the presence of different concentrations of potassium iodide. It has been shown that the photo-colorimetric titration can be used as a method for estimating the amylose contents of starches. The shapes of these titration curves are altered by changes in the concentrations of the reactants and of potassium iodide.

The iodine-complexes of starch and amylose have been precipitated from solution in the presence of different concentrations of iodine, potassium iodide and sodium chloride, washed with solutions of sodium chloride and sodium sulphate, and finally analysed for determining the starch-iodine ratio. This ratio has been found to remain practically unchanged in all these cases, the actual values ranging between 3.6 and 4.0 glucose units per atom of iodine. The significance of the results has been discussed and the formation of a chemical compound of starch and iodine in the precipitated complex has been suggested.

Since the interesting colour reaction between starch and iodine was first discovered by Stromeyer in 1813, there have been numerous investigations on the nature of this interaction, but a completely satisfactory explanation is not yet forthcoming. The earlier workers held divergent views on the subject and variously considered the starch-iodine complex to be (i) a chemical compound (*cf.* Mylius, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 688; Rouvier, *Compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 128, 749; Euler and Myrbäch, *Arkiv Kem. Min. Geol.*, 1922, 8, No. 9, 1; *et seq.*), (ii) a solid solution (*cf.* Küster, *Annalen*, 1894, 283, 360) or (iii) an adsorption complex (*cf.* Lottermoser, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1921, 34, 427; 1924, 37, 84). They all considered the reaction of iodine with starch as a whole. But recent work of Meyer and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 845) has shown that common starch is a heterogeneous substance, being made up of two components, amylose and amylopectin, differing from one another structurally and in their reactions with iodine. Amylose gives a pure blue colour and amylopectin, a reddish purple colour with iodine. This difference in reactivity with iodine has been utilised for estimating the relative proportions of these components in natural starches. Thus, Hassid and McCready (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1154) have developed a colorimetric method and Bates, French and Rundle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 142) an electrometric method for the estimation of amylose in starches, both being based on the differential reactivity of the starch fractions with iodine. On account of these researches, the study of the nature of the interaction between iodine and the individual fractions of starch has assumed increased importance.

Since it is now being generally accepted that the molecules of amylose consist of linear chains and those of amylopectin of a branched structure, attempts have been made to offer interpretations of the starch-iodine reaction in terms of molecular configuration. According to Freudenberg and co-workers (*Naturwissenschaften*, 1939, 27, 850), the amylose molecule has a helical structure, having a hydrocarbon-like interior in which iodine molecules can enter forming a solid solution. Rundle and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*,

1944, 66, 111, 2116) also confirmed the helical configuration of the amylose chain. From potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations they concluded that iodine forms a true compound with the amylose component of starch, the composition remaining constant only when formed at a given iodide concentration. The iodine molecules are arranged linearly inside the helix parallel to its axis. Iodide or tri-iodide ions can enter the helix and replace iodine molecules and thereby alter the ratio between starch and iodine in the complex. They found that six to eight glucose units correspond to each atom of iodine in the complex, the lower figure representing the limiting value for zero concentration of potassium iodide. According to these authors, amylopectin forms a much less stable red complex, and the nature of this interaction resembles that of adsorption or solid solution.

While investigating the characteristics of a number of starch varieties, involving their fractionation, certain peculiarities in the reaction between starch and iodine were noticed by the present authors, which could not be explained on the basis of the existing theories. It was therefore considered to be of interest to pursue the subject further, with a view to throwing further light, if possible, on the nature of this interaction. Recourse has been taken to the use of a photo-electric colorimeter for following the course of the interaction between starch and iodine, by noting the changes in the intensity of the blue colour produced. Electrometric titrations of starch with iodine, as suggested by Bates, French and Rundle (*loc. cit.*) have been carried out for comparison. Another part of this work has been devoted to the precipitation and isolation of starch-iodine complex, prepared under a variety of conditions and determination of its composition by analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Starch Samples.—Potato starch was isolated from the raw tubers in this laboratory. Shoti (*Curcuma zeodoria*) starch was obtained by the courtesy of Messrs. Indian Research Institute, Ltd., Calcutta, and was purified by thorough washing. They were analysed for starch contents by the method given in A.O.A.C. (1939, p. 359). In all the tables given, the quantities of starch have been expressed in terms of the anhydrous starch contents as found by analysis.

Isolation of Amylose.—Amylose was isolated from potato starch by diffusion in warm water according to the procedure described by Hassid and McCready (*loc. cit.*). The anhydrous weight of the amylose has been used in all relevant calculations.

Potentiometric Titrations.—The starch (or amylose) was dissolved in dilute caustic potash solution, neutralised with dilute hydriodic acid and diluted with water so that the solution contained 0.01 to 0.04% of the starch and the concentration of potassium iodide was 0.05 *N*. This was titrated with a 0.001*N* solution of iodine containing 0.05*N*-potassium iodide, and the changes in iodine activity were followed by measuring the potentials of a bright platinum electrode dipped in the solution against a saturated calomel electrode, using a Leeds and Northrup potentiometer. The potentials have been plotted against the resulting concentrations of iodine in Fig. 1. The same figure also contains a blank titration curve of water containing 0.05*N*-potassium iodide with iodine of the same strength as used for the other titrations.

FIG. 1
Potentiometric titrations.

Titration using Photo-electric Colorimeter.—The starch or amylose was made into a 0.01 to 0.04 % solution and titrated with a 0.001*N* solution of iodine, exactly as under 'potentiometric titrations,' but using a Klett-Summerson photo-electric colorimeter for measuring the intensities of colour during the titration. The curves obtained by plotting the colorimeter readings against the resulting concentrations of the iodine added are given in Fig. 3.

Another set of titrations of amylose and shoti starch with iodine was carried out using the photo-electric colorimeter, but under slightly different conditions as follows: The starch or amylose was dissolved in dilute caustic soda solution and the solution neutralised with hydrochloric acid, thus avoiding the introduction of iodide ions at this stage. The starch solution was made up to a strength of 0.001 to 0.002% and a 0.0157*N* solution of iodine containing 0.157*N*-potassium iodide was used for the titration. In some cases, known amounts of potassium iodide were added to the starch solution before titration in order to study the effect of different concentrations of this salt on the course of titration. These titration curves are shown in Fig. 4. The initial portions of these curves have been magnified in Fig. 5.

Isolation and Analysis of Starch-iodine Complex.—In the preliminary experiments potato starch, shoti starch and amylose (from potato starch) were employed. 0.5 G. of the amylose or 1.0 g. of the starch was dissolved in 20 ml. of a dilute solution of caustic soda and then acidified slightly with hydrochloric acid. To this was added 20 ml. of a 20% solution of sodium chloride and then 2.5 ml. of a 12% solution of iodine containing 20% potassium iodide. The starch-iodine complex was thrown down as a precipitate and the mixture was shaken up thoroughly for 5 minutes and then centrifuged. The supernatant liquid containing the free iodine was decanted off and the precipitated complex was washed with a further 50 ml. of 20% sodium chloride solution. This

was found to be adequate, as further washing with the salt solution failed to extract any further free iodine from the residue. The precipitate was washed out with 15 ml. of an $N/10$ solution of sodium thiosulphate and the suspension titrated with an $N/10$ solution of iodine.

FIG. 2

Similar experiments were then carried out under three different conditions, namely,

- (i) precipitation of the complex in the presence of varying concentrations of potassium iodide and washing the precipitate with a 20% sodium chloride solution;
- (ii) precipitation in the presence of varying concentrations of sodium chloride* and washing with a 20% sodium chloride solution; and
- (iii) precipitation in the presence of varying concentrations of potassium iodide and washing with a 10% sodium sulphate solution.

* The reaction mixture contained potassium iodide at a concentration of 0.043N, this being derived from the iodine solution added for the interaction.

FIG. 3

Photo-colorimetric titrations.

FIG. 4

For (i) and (iii) the starch was dissolved in a 10% caustic potash solution which was subsequently neutralised with hydriodic acid. For (ii) the starch was dissolved in a 10% caustic soda solution and the solution neutralised with hydrochloric acid. Iodine was added in the form of a 12% solution containing 20% potassium iodide, and 2.5 ml. of the solution were added in each case. Potassium iodide or sodium chloride was added at this stage, in the form of a concentrated solution, sufficient to raise the concentration of the salt to the desired level. When the complex was formed in the

presence of relatively low concentrations (0.046*N* and 0.176*N*) of potassium iodide, the precipitation of the complex was incomplete. In order to produce complete precipitation, the same salt, as was used subsequently for washing the precipitate *viz.*, sodium chloride or sodium sulphate, was added in solid form. The resulting concentration of the salt was 5% and 3% respectively for solutions containing 0.046*N* and 0.176 *N*-potassium iodide. The complex, which was now thrown down as a precipitate, was separated from the solution by centrifuging. The supernatant liquid in the centrifuge tubes was decanted off and the precipitate was washed with 50 ml. of the salt solution. Washing was done only once in series (i) and (ii) as in the previous experiment, but in (iii) the precipitate was washed three times with sodium sulphate solution. In each washing, the sediment was mixed thoroughly with the salt solution, the suspension was centrifuged and the supernatant liquid decanted off.

FIG. 5

The precipitate was washed out of the tubes using 15 ml. of a 0.1 *N* solution of sodium thiosulphate and this suspension was titrated with a 0.1*N* solution of iodine.

For calculating the ratio of starch to iodine in the complex, it was assumed that all the starch, taken initially, was present in the precipitated complex. In order to test the correctness of this assumption, two experiments were made in which the precipitated starch-iodine complex, after being taken in the sodium thiosulphate solution, was analysed for starch by acid hydrolysis method. The results given in Table III show good agreement between the quantities of starch taken and those found by analysis of the complex. Consequently, no further determinations of starch in the final suspensions were made in the other experiments.

In series (i) and (ii), only potato starch was used, but in series (iii), both amylose and potato starch were employed. The results of these experiments are given in Tables IV and V.

In the experiments of series (i) to (iii), varying amounts of water had to be added to bring the concentrations of the added salts to the desired levels, and this resulted in

a variation of the concentration of iodine in the reaction mixture. In Table V, these concentrations of iodine have also been given.

TABLE I

Potentiometric and photo-colorimetric titrations of starch with iodine.

Conc. of iodine=0.001 N. Vol. of titrant=50 ml.

Mode of titration.	Variety of starch (or amylose).	Quantity of starch taken.	Quantity of iodine combining at the end-point.	Ratio of Iodine : starch at end-point.	No. of glucose units per atom of iodine.	Amylose content.
Potentiometer	Amylose	0.0052 g.	0.000803 g.	0.155	5.07	100%
"	Potato starch	0.0161	0.000751	0.047	16.85	30.32
"	Shoti starch	0.0173	0.000919	0.053	14.79	34.20
Photo-electric colorimeter	Amylose	0.0025	0.000380	0.152	5.16	100
"	Potato starch	0.0076	0.000334	0.044	17.83	28.94
"	Shoti starch	0.0076	0.000327	0.043	18.22	28.28

TABLE II

Photo-colorimetric titration.

Conc. of iodine=0.0157 N. Vol. of titrant=500 ml.

Titration curve No.	Conc. of KI added.	Variety of starch (or amylose).	Quantity of starch taken.	Quantity of iodine added at colour transition.	Ratio of iodine : starch at the colour transition.
1	Nil	Amylose	0.00501 g.	0.0086 g.	1.72
2	0.08 N	"	"	0.0040	0.80
3	Nil	Shoti starch	0.00595	0.0061	1.03
4	0.08	"	"	0.0038	0.64
5	0.32	"	"	0.0038	0.64

TABLE III

Expt.	Starch taken.	Quantity of starch found.
(A)	0.857 g.	0.855 g.
(B)	0.687	0.670

TABLE IV

Analysis of starch-iodine precipitate.

Quantity of starch (or amylose) taken.	Quantity of iodine found by titration.	No. of glucose units per atom of iodine.
Amylose (0.4133 g.)	0.0889 g.	3.82
Potato starch (0.7326 g.)	0.1431	4.00
Shoti starch (0.6806 g.)	0.1372	3.90

TABLE V

*Starch-iodine ratios in amylose and potato starch-iodine complexes.**Amylose content of starch=27.2%*

Potato starch-iodine. precipitated in presence of KI. Washed with NaCl.			Potato starch-iodine. Precipitated in presence of NaCl. Washed with NaCl			Potato starch-iodine. Precipitated in presence of KI. Washed with Na ₂ SO ₄			Amylose-iodine. precipitated in presence of KI. Washed with Na ₂ SO ₄		
(1)			(2)			(3a)			(3b)		
Conc. iodine.	Conc. KI.	No. of glucose units.*	Conc. iodine.	Conc. NaCl	No. of glucose units.*	Conc. iodine.	Conc. KI	No. of glucose units.*	Conc. iodine.	Conc. KI	No. of glucose units
0.078 N	0.176N	3.71	0.045 N	0.85 N	3.60	0.026 N	0.046 N	3.83	0.012N	0.046 N	3.94
								3.84			
0.059	0.450	3.86	0.033	1.70	3.65	0.065	0.176	3.67	0.025	0.176	3.76
					3.75			3.75			
					3.65						
0.047	0.530	3.75	0.027	2.44	3.67	0.058	0.530	3.94
		3.67			3.74			3.83			
					3.67						
0.039	1.210	3.86	0.027	3.30	3.70	0.035	1.210	3.99	0.033	1.210	3.94
		3.79						3.90			
Mean	..	3.74	3.67	3.84	3.88

* Per atom of iodine.

DISCUSSION

Potentiometric and Photo-colorimetric Titrations.

The potentiometric titration curves for amylose and starches in Fig. 1 have distinct inflexions, which may be taken to represent the end-points of the amylose-iodine reaction. The corresponding $dE/d[I_2]-[I_2]$ curves (in which E represents the E.M.F. and $[I_2]$ the concentration of iodine) given in Fig. 2 enable one to locate the inflexion points. Bates, French and Rundle (*loc. cit.*), who also obtained similar titration curves, assumed the point where the slope first showed a rapid rise as the end-point of the amylose-iodine reaction. But subsequently Baldwin, Bear and Rundle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 111) who observed discrepancies between the results obtained by potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations, remarked that the complex formation is not completed at this point, on account of the partial dissociation of the complex near the saturation point. It appears, however, that it would be more appropriate to take the inflexion points as representing the end-points, as is done in the potentiometric (p_H) titration curve of a moderately strong acid with an alkali where partial hydrolysis of the salt takes place near the equivalence point. The uncombined iodine left in the system at this inflexion point can be estimated with the help of curve 'X' in Fig. 1. The quantity of iodine actually entering into combination with the amylose at the inflexion point can therefore be obtained by deducting the uncombined iodine from the total amount of iodine added at this point. If it be assumed, as has been done by Bates, French and Rundle (*loc. cit.*), that only amylose reacts with iodine up to this point and that consequently the amounts of iodine combining with a

given quantity of starch are proportional to the amylose contents, the latter can be calculated from the potentiometric titration curve by comparing it with that for pure amylose. The ratios of starch to iodine at the inflexion points and the amylose contents of potato and shoti starches calculated in this manner have been given in Table I.

The titration curves in Fig. 3, obtained by using the photo-electric colorimeter, and under the same conditions as in the potentiometric titrations, also show breaks in their slopes. The curves rise almost linearly in the initial stages, then take a sharp bend and finally run nearly flat. Supposing that only amylose reacts with iodine in the initial stage, the steep rise in the titration curve would represent the formation of the blue amylose-iodine complex. In such a curve, the end-point would be represented by the point of intersection of the initial and final slopes. Obtaining the end-points in this manner and proceeding on the same lines as before, the percentages of amylose in potato and shoti starches have been calculated and given in Table I.

Comparison of the two sets of figures in Table I for the amylose contents of potato and shoti starches shows a small difference. Mukherjee and Bhattacharyya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1945, 8, 4) obtained the values 27.2% and 31.3% respectively for the amylose contents of potato and shoti starches by following a colorimetric method which is a slight modification of that described by Hassid and McCready (*loc. cit.*). It thus appears that titration with iodine using the photo-electric colorimeter may be regarded to constitute an additional method for the determination of the amylose contents of starches. It will, however, be noticed from a study of the titration curves in Figs. 1 and 2, that the curves for amylose show sharper breaks or inflexion points than those for the starches investigated. This difference would indicate the possibility of the other constituent of starch, i.e., amylopectin, taking some part in the reaction.

Baldwin, Bear and Rundle (*loc. cit.*) stress the necessity of using low concentrations of iodine for spectrophotometric titrations, as the iodine then first forms a complex with amylose alone and the molecular extinction coefficient is nearly independent of the amylopectin impurity. Another set of titrations was therefore carried out with still lower concentrations of starch, viz., 0.001 to 0.004% and under such conditions that the concentrations of iodine in the starch solution during the titration were of a much lower order than in the previous titrations. These titrations were also carried out in the presence of varying concentrations of potassium iodide (*vide* Fig. 4). The curves for amylose and shoti starch (Fig. 4), obtained without the addition of potassium iodide, show significant differences in shape from the corresponding curves in Fig. 3. In the initial stages the curves remain flat but rise subsequently and pass through inflexion points, finally becoming flat again. The initial flat portion (*vide* also Fig. 5) indicates either the absence of interaction or the formation of a colourless complex, at these low concentrations. But the slight rise in iodine activity in the initial stages of the potentiometric titration curves (Fig. 1) suggests that the former supposition is probably correct.

In the presence of potassium iodide (*vide* curves in Fig. 4) the initial flat portion is abbreviated, so that the curves rise steeply from the beginning of the titration. This shows that the potassium iodide facilitates the reaction between amylose and iodine at extremely low concentrations of the reactants, where normally no interaction would take place in its absence.

The presence of potassium iodide not only increases the initial slope but at the same time enhances the maximum intensity of colour attained during the titration. This is in accord with the observations of Baldwin, Bear and Rundle (*loc. cit.*) made by spectrophotometric titrations of amylose.

It was noticed during these titrations that the light blue colour, produced by the first addition of iodine, grows deeper as the titration proceeds and at a certain stage the colour changes to a greenish shade. This change can be detected within 0.25 ml. of the iodine added. The points at which the transition of colour was noticeable have been marked with arrows in the titration curves in Fig. 4. The change from blue to green colour may be produced by the superposition of the blue colour of the amylose-iodine complex and the yellow colour of free iodine, which would be expected to be present in the system after the formation of this blue complex is complete. If this supposition were correct, these transition points would give a measure of the amylose contents of starches. Calculations of the ratios of iodine to starch, calculated from the points of colour transition, given in Table II, however, fail to show a direct correspondence between these and the corresponding ratios given in column 5 of Table I.

If the amylose-iodine complex be regarded as a chemical compound, a definite stoichiometric relationship between the reactants should be expected. The number of glucose residues (of amylose or starch) corresponding to each atom of iodine, calculated at the end-points of the titration curves in Figs. 1 and 3, are given in column 6 of Table I. The figures for amylose calculated from the potentiometric and the photo-colorimetric titration curves in the presence of 0.05*N*-potassium iodide come to 5.07 and 5.16 respectively. The corresponding figures, found by Rundle and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) from potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations of amylose in the presence of 0.05*N*-potassium iodide are 7.2 and 8.4 respectively. In both sets of figures the optical methods are found to give higher values than those obtained by the potentiometric method, but the difference in magnitude between their values and those obtained here could not be explained. The low values of the ratio found in our experiments are significant in view of the fact that according to the hypothesis put forward by Rundle and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) six is the minimum number of glucose units corresponding to each atom of iodine in the complex attainable at infinite dilution of potassium iodide.

Isolation of the Starch-iodine Complex.

The results obtained by the isolation and analysis of the starch-iodine complex (Tables IV and V) provide more direct evidence for the ratio of starch to iodine in the complex. Since amylopectin is considered to have a much weaker affinity for iodine than amylose (Rundle and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) and common starches contain a much higher proportion of amylopectin than of amylose, these starches would be expected to form complexes with iodine having larger starch-iodine ratios than amylose itself. But the figures in Tables IV and V show that this ratio for both potato and shoti starches are almost identical with that for amylose, the actual values ranging between 3.6 and 4.0 glucose units per atom of iodine. It will, however, be noticed that in series 3(a) and (b), where the washing of the precipitate was more complete, most of these figures approach nearer to the upper limit. Further, these values

are significantly lower than those found by potentiometric and photo-colorimetric titrations of amylose solutions.

Influence of Potassium Iodide.—It has already been shown how the presence of iodide ions influences the shapes of the titration curves of starch solutions with iodine. Rundle and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) postulated that iodide ions can penetrate into the complex and displace iodine molecules. This would result in an increase of the starch-iodine ratio, and the above authors found this ratio to be as high as 8 glucose units per atom of iodine in the presence of 0.05*N*-potassium iodide. In the present series of experiments the concentration of potassium iodide in the starch solution at the time of precipitation of the complex was varied between the limits 0.043*N* and 1.21*N*, but, as the results in Table V show, this had no perceptible effect on the starch-iodine ratios of the precipitated complex.

Influence of other Salts.—The starch-iodine complex, after precipitation, had to be washed free from any iodine mechanically adhering to it, but the use of water was not practicable on account of the peptisation of the coagulum when washed with water. Sodium chloride (20%) was therefore used in the preliminary experiments (Table IV) as well as in series (i) and (ii).

In order to find out if the concentration of sodium chloride used would have any effect on the composition of the complex, in series (ii) the concentration of potassium iodide was kept constant at 0.043*N*, while that of sodium chloride was varied between 0.85*N* and 3.30*N*. It will be seen from Table V that no detectable variation of the starch-iodine ratio resulted from these alterations.

Again, in series (iii) of the experiments, sodium chloride was replaced by sodium sulphate in order to see if the divalent SO_4^{--} ion would have any influence. But the results fail to show any marked change in the starch-iodine ratio by this treatment. In fact, the average value of this ratio in series (iii) was 3.86 as against 3.74 and 3.67 glucose units per atom of iodine for series (i) and (ii) respectively.

Influence of the Concentration of Iodine.—In the experiments carried out under series (iii), the iodine concentration was varied in the reaction mixtures between the limits 0.012 *N* and 0.078 *N*. But it will be found from Table V that these changes did not affect the composition of the complexes.

Further work on this problem is in progress.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The interaction between iodine and starch has been studied in the solution phase, by potentiometric and photo-colorimetric titrations and in the solid phase by salting out the starch-iodine complex and analysing the precipitate.

2. In the interaction of starch and iodine in solution, only the amylose component appears to combine with iodine. The course of the interaction and the end-points of the titrations are altered by the presence of iodide ions. Interchange between iodine molecules in the complex and iodide ions in solution, as suggested by Rundle and co-workers (*loc. cit.*), possibly takes place, resulting in a variation of the starch-iodine ratio of the complex.

3. The starch-iodine complex, in the solid-phase, *i.e.*, in the precipitated condition, shows, in contrast to its behaviour in solution, a remarkable constancy of composition. The ratio of starch to iodine remains practically independent of the concentrations of iodine, potassium iodide and/or of the other salts present in the system at the time of formation or of washing the precipitate.

4. In the precipitated condition, the iodine-complexes of both amylose and whole starch show an identical starch-iodine ratio. The mean value of this ratio is near about 4.0 glucose units for each atom of iodine. This value is lower than that obtained for amylose by potentiometric or photo-colorimetric titrations in the solution phase.

5. The difference in reactivity between amylose and amylopectin towards iodine is being generally attributed to the difference in their molecular structure, *i.e.*, in the lengths of the glucose chains. The observation recorded in the preceding paragraph indicates that under the conditions of precipitation of the starch-iodine complex, changes occur which practically obliterate the effects of these structural differences and the two starch components, amylose and amylopectin, behave similarly in their interaction with iodine.

6. The constancy of the composition of the precipitated starch-iodine complex indicates some sort of chemical combination in a definite stoichiometric ratio in the interaction between iodine and starch. The approximate formula of the complex may be written as $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_{8.8}I_{2.2}$.

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